

CESSDA Network of Partners

CESSDA Widening Meeting
Skopje | 5 – 6 November 2019

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Outline

- ◊ Widening Activities 2019 & 2020 - quick overview
- ◊ Widening & Outreach - a possible new CESSDA Pillar
- ◊ CESSDA funding model
- ◊ Structure of membership and collaboration

Widening Activities 2019

- ◊ Widening Meeting in Skopje
- ◊ CESSDA Mentorship Programme
- ◊ Helpdesk / Support Service for Data Archives
- ◊ Additional activity: national event

Widening Activities 2020

- ◊ Cuts in the budget => cuts in the plans
- ◊ The modified project is still under development

- ◊ The event: jointly with the CESSDA Training Days
- ◊ Mentorship Programme
(including visits / small national events)
- ◊ Upgrading the Resource Directory
- ◊ Monitoring the developments at the CESSDA Partners
- ◊ Helpdesk / Support Service for Data Archives

Challenges

- ◆ Pan-European coverage
(widening membership & developing the network of partners)
- ◆ Growing membership; diversity; modes of collaboration
- ◆ Widening in all meanings (new data types, new demands from the research community, new services)
- ◆ Changing RI environment (EU scientific policies, Open Access, FAIR data, EOSC, clustering, monitoring and evaluation...)
- ◆ CESSDA visibility and visible impact to research and RIs, disseminating CESSDA tools and knowledge
- ◆ CESSDA on a global playground

CESSDA response

GUIDE
WP 3 on Widening
and Cooperation

CESSDA SaW &
Work Plan tasks on
Widening Activities

Other strategies
on external
collaboration

Widening & Outreach
CESSDA Pillar

UNDER DISCUSSION
to be developed
during 2020

- ◆ Widening & Network of Partners
- ◆ Strengthening: imature SPs, compatibility
- ◆ Strengthening: sustainable institutional settings
- ◆ Widening the external collaboration
- ◆ Impact (research, RIs, stakeholders)
- ◆ Global player

CESSDA funding model 2017-2021

Change?

- ◇ sustainability
- ◇ stronger CESSDA
- ◇ (un-)balance
- ◇ (ir-)responsibility
- ◇ (in-)justice (large vs. small)
- ◇ opportunities, returns

■ Norway

■ Germany

■ United Kingdom

■ France

■ Netherlands

■ Belgium

■ Greece

■ Czech Republic

■ Portugal

■ Sweden

■ Hungary

■ Austria

■ Serbia

■ Switzerland

■ Denmark

■ Finland

■ Slovakia

■ Croatia

■ North Macedonia

■ Slovenia

Challenges for widening

- ◆ Promotion of widening by more structured membership and more formalised wide collaborative network
 - ◆ Is formal partnership beneficial as a first step to membership?
 - ◆ Is formal partnership beneficial to establishing closer longer-term collaboration?